

Sample 22a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0031
	{Si}	44.8
	{Fe}	18.8
	{Al, Si}	11.5
	{Si, Fe}	3.0
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.7
	{Al, Si, Ca}	2.5
	{Ca}	2.5
	{Al, Si, K}	1.7
	{Al}	1.2
	{Mg, Si}	1.2
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.0
	{Mg, Ca}	1.0
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.9
	{Si, Ca HiP}	0.9
	{Ca, Fe}	0.8
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.7
	{Na, Si}	0.6
	{Si, K}	0.4
	{Al, S}	0.4
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.4
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.3
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Al, Ca}	0.2
	{Ti}	0.2
	{P, Ca}	0.2
	{Zn-LA1}	0.1
	{Mg, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Al, Fe}	0.1
	{S, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Ti}	0.1
	{Cl}	0.1
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

		area %
	Sinter	1.9
	Pellet	4.9
	Ore preparation undifferentiated	8.2
	Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
	Ore / hot metal	1.3
	BOF converter slag	0.2
	BOF converter slag slopping	0.8
	Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.7
	Desulph slag	1.2
	Ca-aluminate slag	0.1
	Blast furnace slag	0.0
	Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.2
	Olivine flux	0.8
	Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
	Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.4
	Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
	MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
	Tundish gunning mass	0.0
	Alumina	0.2
	Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
	Rich in Zn-compounds	0.7
	Fe-metal rich	0.0
	Coal and cokes or soil	12.4
	Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.5
	Carbon rich - other	1.7
	Cement or BOF converter	0.6
	Cement	0.8
	Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
	Ti-rich paint	0.1
	Ba-sulphate bearing	0.4
	Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
	Al-corrosion/salts	1.0
	Salt or salt layer	0.0
	Qz-day-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	42.7
	Qz-day-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	13.9
	Misc silicates including natural	0.3
	Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
	Apatite	0.0
	Ca-Al-silicate dominated	1.0
	Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
	Na-sulphate rich	0.0
	Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
	Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
	Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
	Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
	Unassigned other	0.3

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	14.9
Site - ore / hot metal	1.3
Site - slag	3.9
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	2.0
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	1.4
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.2
Site - scrap	0.7
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	12.4
Site - carbon-rich other	0.5
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	1.7
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.6
Urban	2.2
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	42.7
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	13.9
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.3
Unknown	1.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.3

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 22b

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0033
	{Si}	41.8
	{Fe}	22.8
	{Al, Si}	12.4
	{Si, Fe}	3.6
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.1
	{Al, Si, K}	2.1
	{Na, Al, Si}	2.1
	{Ca}	1.9
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.8
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.9
	{Si, Ca HiP}	0.9
	{Al}	0.8
	{Ca, Fe}	0.8
	{Al, S}	0.6
	{Mg, Si}	0.5
	{Na, Si}	0.4
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.4
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.4
	{Si, K}	0.4
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.4
	{Mg, Ca}	0.4
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.4
	{Zn-LA1}	0.3
	{Al, Ca}	0.2
	{Mg, Fe}	0.2
	{Na, S}	0.1
	{Al, Fe}	0.1
	{Ti}	0.1
	{Si, Fe}	0.1
	{S, Ca}	0.1
	{P, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Cl}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

141 μm

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	3.6
Pellet	5.7
Ore preparation undifferentiated	9.5
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	1.3
BOF converter slag	0.4
BOF converter slag slopping	0.5
Slag BOF converter or desulph	2.4
Desulph slag	0.3
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.4
Olivine flux	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.1
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.1
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.3
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.6
Fe-metal rich	0.2
Coal and cokes or soil	13.8
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.2
Carbon rich - other	4.6
Cement or BOF converter	0.7
Cement	1.1
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.2
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	42.6
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	10.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.1
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.1

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	18.8
Site - ore / hot metal	1.3
Site - slag	3.6
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.5
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.1
Site - flux / refractory	0.1
Site - refractory	0.3
Site - scrap	0.6
Urban + site - scrap	0.2
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	13.8
Site - carbon-rich other	1.2
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	4.6
Urban; rarely site - slag	0.7
Urban	1.3
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	42.6
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	10.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.1
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.1

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 22c

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0024
	{Si}	49.0
	{Fe}	17.1
	{Al, Si}	10.7
	{Al, Si, K}	4.6
	{Si, Fe}	3.0
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.2
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.6
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.6
	{Ca}	1.4
	{Mg, Al, Si}	1.3
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.9
	{Si, Ca HiP}	0.8
	{Ca, Fe}	0.5
	{Mg, Si}	0.5
	{Al}	0.5
	{Mg, Ca}	0.4
	{Na, Si}	0.4
	{Si, K}	0.4
	{Zn-LA1}	0.3
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{P, Ca}	0.2
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Mg, Fe}	0.2
	{Cl}	0.2
	{Ti}	0.1
	{Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, P, Ca}	0.1
	{Cl}	0.1
	{Mg}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	1.1
Pellet	4.8
Ore preparation undifferentiated	6.3
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.7
BOF converter slag	0.6
BOF converter slag slopping	0.3
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.9
Desulph slag	0.8
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.2
Olivine flux	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.2
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.1
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.6
Fe-metal rich	0.5
Coal and cokes or soil	20.5
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.4
Carbon rich - other	3.7
Cement or BOF converter	0.4
Cement	0.9
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.1
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.2
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	48.4
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	6.9
Misc silicates including natural	0.1
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.2

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	12.2
Site - ore / hot metal	0.7
Site - slag	2.6
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.2
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.2
Site - flux / refractory	0.1
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.6
Urban + site - scrap	0.5
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	20.5
Site - carbon-rich other	1.4
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	3.7
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.4
Urban	1.2
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	48.4
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	6.9
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.2
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.3

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels